

PLAGIARISM: ADDICTION OR A NEW SOURCE TYPE?

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ANNOTATION Have you ever plagiarized? If not, I advise you... wait, are you from the Earth? Supposing that, it would be really interesting for you to read the given below so that no one could steal your works since nowadays every person tends to copy someone's ideas, thoughts and etc. Don't make it a habit, but rather try your skills, it is much more pleasant!

KEY WORDS: citing, plagiarism checker, online resources, types of plagiarism: academic plagiarism, patchwork, paraphrasing, complete, self-plagiarism, accidental, source-based, direct or verbatim.

АННОТАЦИЯ Вы когда-нибудь занимались плагиатом? Если нет... погодите, а вы точно с нашей планеты? Что ж, если это так, мне кажется, после интересного чтения, данного ниже, вы откроете для себя много полезного, и никто уже не сможет красть ваши работы, так как сейчас каждый человек склонен копировать чьи-то идеи, мысли и т.д. Не привыкайте думать за чужой счет, а лучше старайтесь проявлять собственные навыки, это куда более приятнее!

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: подпись источника, проверка на плагиат, интернет-ресурсы, виды плагиата: академический, лоскутный, перефразирование, полный, само плагиат, случайный, основанный на источнике, прямой или дословный.

To begin with, finding information nowadays is becoming viral. Humanity tends to enlarge sources in order to make the world library called Net to be even

more than usual. Spreading various types of text and other media has now multiple ways to be read, seen and perceived. Whenever someone writes something using new words, this approach broadens the topic and introduces new nuances to the addressed subject. Consequently, the person who reads these words later can interpret a certain topic differently, thereby introducing new research angles. When a topic is explained using original and specific words, the audience has an opportunity to connect with the writer on a higher level.

Frankly speaking, the more opportunities having a great deal of information we get to know, the more hazard may appear. And one of them, which is going to be described is plagiarism - a 'capital' offence in most institutions and it can lead to expulsion or other forms of disciplinary actions towards the students who practice it. In brief, this is representation of another author's language, thoughts, ideas or expressions as one's own original work. When students fail to use their own words and/or neglect to give credit to the original writers, this is also known as plagiarism.

However, in some situations, human cannot be aware of making someone's idea their property because of not *citing* or using special websites as *plagiarism checker*. To be honest, researching databases, institution's library and other *online resources* (encyclopedias, blogs, etc.) has its chance to be turned into a problematic process if one won't add author's name or give proper link from where the information was taken. Although the movie industries may be affected by the vice, *academic plagiarism* has been prevalent in recent decades in learning institutions. To develop good writing skills, academicians need to uphold the practice of intellectual honesty and avoid plagiarism.

It's not a secret *plagiarism has different types*:

- *mosaic or patchwork* - the writer often takes the work of another person and "patches them together" as his own (according to Klausman, 1999);
- *paraphrasing* - writer takes the work partially ; the problem usually occurs because most students do not know the correct way to paraphrase the article or book and give credit to the original author;

- *complete* - a person completely copies someone else's work such as a research paper, article, image, etc, and represents it as their own work. This form of plagiarism is similar to identity theft or stealing;
- *self-plagiarism* - recycling your own past work;
- *accidental* - when a writer commits some form of plagiarism without meaning to;
- *source-based* - when a writer (intentionally or unintentionally) does not cite a source fully and accurately;
- *direct or verbatim* - directly copying someone else's words;

Writing an article, a research paper, an assignment, or essay can hardly ever be said to be complete *without checking* to ensure its uniqueness. And with the alarming rate of plagiarism, it's always easy to tell if the content is new with the help of a [plagiarism checker](#) or special charts.

As long as you work with what is supposed to be “original” written content, you need a plagiarism checker to verify your content's originality and uniqueness. The one I recommend is the [SmallSEOTools.com](#). The tool allows to check any piece of content to be sure that it is unique and the content will not get penalized by any search engine.

But living on the Earth with an eight billion number of populations, every individual can plagiarize, not on account of lacking assurance in providing original source, but only copy/pasting. It seems as if plagiarism is an inherent part of the Internet. With millions of blog posts published every day, there is bound to be some overlap in information. However, that is no excuse not to be vigilant in your own effort to avoid passing other people's work off as your own.

By being conscientious in your writing efforts, keeping track of your information sources and providing links, you not only safeguard yourself against charges of stealing but also insert yourself into the broader conversation.

To sum up, looking for information requires special attitude so that to avoid stealing one's thoughts. For example, many basic textbooks or dictionaries contain passages that come very close to plagiarism. In most of these cases the charge of

plagiarism would be unjust because there are a limited number of ways in which basic information can be conveyed. Many students, being unable to distinguish visible copy/pasting spread this kind of approach on others and make plagiarism a certain form of source which is going to be one of the world's disasters among inappropriate use and impact of information on adolescents and adults (information crisis), pollution, problems regarding deforestation, etc. *Don't let plagiarism transform into a global monster, be creative and make your ideas unique!*

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